

Ring-Closure of *o*-Aminophenylsemicarbazides to Benzotriazines.

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(Experiments by Frl. Hedwig Skzypczik and P. S. Mayuranathan).

In a series of papers Guha and co-workers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 83 ; 1928, 5, 439) have described reactions involving the ring-closure of carbonic acid derivatives of *o*-aminophenylhydrazine. To the products obtained by the action of *o*-aminophenylhydrazine upon potassium ethyl xanthogenate and carbamide, they ascribe the formulæ 3-mercapto-1:2-dihydro-1:2:4-benzotriazine (I) and 3-hydroxy-1:2-dihydro-1:2:4-benzotriazine (II) respectively.

(I)

(II)

o-Nitrophenylsemicarbazide (III), *o*-nitrophenylthiosemicarbazide (IV) and methyl *o*-nitrophenyldithiocarbazine (V) were obtained from *o*-nitrophenylhydrazine by the action of (a) cyanic acid, (b) thiocyanic acid and (c) carbon disulphide, alcoholic potash and methyl iodide. It was stated there that the reduction of the nitro to the amino group is accompanied by simultaneous splitting of water or hydrogen sulphide resulting in the formation of 3-amino-1:2-dihydro-1:2:4-benzotriazine (VI) from (III) and (IV) and 3-methylthiol-1:2-dihydro-1:2:4-benzotriazine (VII) from (V).

Arndt (*Ber.*, 1913, 46, 3522) found that *o*-nitrophenylguanidine (VIII) by warming with alkali formed 3-amino-1-oxo-1:2:4-benzotriazine (IX) which passed on reduction to 3-amino-1:2-dihydro-1:2:4-benzotriazine (VI). This, however, could only be isolated as a

colourless nitrate: the free base suffered instantaneous oxidation to 3-amino-1:2:4-benzotriazine (X).

o-Nitrophenylcarbamide on similar treatment furnished in the end 3-hydroxy-1:2:4-benzotriazine. From *o*-nitrophenylthiocarbamide Arndt and Rosenau (*Ber.*, 1917, 50, 1248) obtained 3-mercapto-1-oxo-1:2:4-benzotriazine, the methylthiol derivative of which yielded on reduction a colourless salt solution of the dihydro-compound: the free base could not be isolated as it suffered immediate aerial oxidation to 3-methylthiol-1:2:4-benzotriazine. Later, Arndt (*Ber.*, 1927, 60, 2598) obtained the same 3-methylthiol-1:2:4-benzotriazine by boiling the azo-compound $\text{Ph}-\text{N}:\text{C}(\text{SCH}_3)-\text{N}:\text{N}-\text{CO}-\text{NH}_2$ with organic solvents. A similar series of reactions were carried out also with the azo-body $\text{Ph}-\text{N}=\text{C}(\text{NH}_2)-\text{N}:\text{N}-\text{C}(\text{SCH}_3)=\text{NH}$ which by thermal decomposition gave directly the compound (X).

It appeared that the stability ascribed to the dihydrobenzotriazines by Guha and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) stood in direct contradiction to Arndt's work. With a view to explain this contradiction, by mutual agreement, the present work was undertaken simultaneously by both of us in our respective laboratories. The compounds (III) and (IV) were reduced exactly according to the method of Guha and the reaction mixture worked up when a base melting at 85° (*cf.* Guha who also gives 85°) was obtained which, however, on further careful purification melted at $101-102^\circ$ and the substance was identified as such to be *o*-phenylenediamine and also in the form of its *p*-nitrobenzal derivative. Under the older experimental conditions the drastic reduction leads to a splitting between the two nitrogen atoms of the hydrazine group.

Now, the question before us was whether the reduction mechanism described by Guha could be realised under more suitable (*i.e.*, milder) conditions. Careful reduction of *o*-nitrophenylthiosemicarbazide (IV)

with a slight excess of stannous chloride and dilute hydrochloric acid, basification of the reaction mixture and repeated extraction with ether, furnished a colourless substance (transitory) which quickly changed to yellow. This substance is identical in all particulars with 3-aminobenzotriazine (X) (Arndt, *loc. cit.*) formed by rapid oxidation of the intermediate dihydro-derivative.

Thus, the compound (X) is now obtained in a third way *viz.*, by ring-closure between positions 3 and 4 of the triazine ring; while it was obtained by Arndt by ring-closure between positions 1 and 2 in one case and between 1 and 6 in another. It follows that the dihydrobenzotriazines possess the properties ascribed to them by Arndt and that they are not formed under Guha's older conditions of experiments.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The preparation of *o*-nitrophenylthiosemicarbazide and its reduction were carried out in the manner indicated previously by Guha (*loc. cit.*). The crystalline product obtained from alcohol and which melted according to Guha at 85°, gave after repeated crystallisation from ligroin and finally from alcohol, colourless crystals melting at 101-102°. This was identified as *o*-phenylenediamine by taking the mixed melting point with a genuine sample (Kahlbaum) as also by taking a mixed melting point of its *p*-nitrobenzal derivative (m.p. 138°) prepared from the diamine thus obtained and that prepared from a genuine sample.

Reduction under Milder Conditions: Formation of 3-Amino-1:2:4-benzotriazine.—*o*-Nitrophenylthiosemicarbazide (1 g.) was boiled under reflux with stannous chloride (4 g.) and 2*N*-hydrochloric acid (10 c.c.) till the solution ceased to give a blue colour with caustic alkali. The solution was made strongly alkaline with 2*N* sodium hydroxide solution and thoroughly shaken with ether. The colourless ethereal layer soon became dark-yellow and began to deposit yellow needles

which dissolved on the further addition of ether. The ether extract was evaporated and the yellow residue recrystallised from alcohol, when yellow needles of aminobenzotriazine were obtained, m.p. 206°. Mixed melting point with a preparation obtained from *o*-nitrophenylguanidine gave no depression.

Both *o*-nitrophenylsemicarbazide and methyl *o*-nitrophenyldithiocarbazinate were prepared as stated by Guha (*loc. cit.*) and the products were in perfect agreement with those previously announced. On reduction according to Guha, the former gave *o*-phenylenediamine.

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